

The Role of NLR (Neutrophil-To-Lymphocyte Ratio) in Predicting Survival in CLD (Chronic Liver Disease) a Correlation with CTP, UKELD and MELD Na Score

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Abstract:

Introduction: Chronic Liver Disease (CLD) is a global health issue with increasing mortality. Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR), a simple marker derived from routine blood tests, has emerged as a potential predictor of disease severity in Chronic Liver Disease. This study investigates the role of NLR in assessing disease severity and predicting clinical outcomes in CLD patient.

Method: This one-year observational study at SRMS IMS, Bareilly, included 140 adult CLD patients admitted to the inpatient department, with chronic liver disease confirmed by ultrasound. Patients with secondary immunodeficiencies, hepatocellular carcinoma, or acute liver failure were excluded. Demographic, clinical, and laboratory data, including NLR from blood counts, were collected. Follow-up assessments monitored patient outcomes. Data analysis was performed using SPSS and MS Excel, with ethical approval from the institutional committee.

Result: The mean NLR in the study was 3.53 ± 1.22 . A significant difference in NLR was found across CTP classes: Class A (2.14 ± 0.78), Class B (3.45 ± 1.18), and Class C (4.14 ± 1.16) with a p-value of 0.01*. NLR showed positive correlations with albumin ($r = 0.171$, $p = 0.044$), bilirubin ($r = 0.363$, $p = 0.001$), and CTP score ($r = 0.386$, $p < 0.001$). Significant differences in albumin ($p = 0.015^*$), prothrombin time ($p = 0.021^*$), and bilirubin ($p = 0.001^*$) were observed across NLR groups.

Conclusion: NLR is a reliable and cost-effective marker for assessing the severity and prognosis of CLD. Its association with liver function parameters and CTP score suggests its potential utility in risk stratification and management of CLD patients. Further studies with larger cohorts are recommended to validate its prognostic value.

Keywords: CLD (Chronic Liver Disease); NLR (Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio); Prognosis; CTP (Child-Turcotte-Pugh); MELD (The Model for End Stage Liver Disease Score); Liver Function; UKELD (United Kingdom Model For End Stage Liver Disease)

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Introduction

Chronic Liver Disease (CLD) is a critical global health issue, placing significant strain on healthcare systems and affecting millions of individuals. Reliable prognostic markers are crucial for assessing disease progression and guiding treatment decisions in CLD. Among emerging markers, the Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR), derived from routine blood counts, has gained attention for its accessibility and cost-effectiveness.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), chronic diseases account for approximately 46% of total disease burden and 59% of global mortality, with nearly 35 million annual deaths

worldwide due to chronic conditions, including liver diseases. [1,2] Cirrhosis ranks as the 11th leading cause of death globally, responsible for 2.2% of deaths and 1.5% of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) in 2016, [3] with 1.32 million deaths in 2017 alone, two-thirds of which were among men. [4] In India, liver disease contributed to 18.3% of the two million liver-related deaths in 2015, underscoring the need for effective healthcare measures. [5]

NLR, representing the balance of innate and adaptive immune responses, has shown promise as a marker of systemic inflammation and stress across various medical condition. [6] In CLD, particularly

cirrhosis, elevated NLR values have been associated with poor prognosis, especially in acute-on-chronic liver failure (ACLF) patients in critical care settings, providing a cost-effective assessment of disease severity. [7]

This study investigates NLR's prognostic potential in CLD by analysing its association with disease severity and clinical outcomes, aiming to advance risk stratification and personalized management in CLD.

Method

This observational study was conducted over a period of one year at SRMS IMS, Bareilly, with a sample size of 140 patients diagnosed with chronic liver disease (CLD) admitted through the inpatient department (IPD). The patients were selected based on specific inclusion criteria, including adults aged 18 years and above with confirmed ultrasound evidence of chronic liver disease, such as low protein levels, high SAAG ascites, or the presence of oesophageal varices without portal or mesenteric venous thrombosis. Patients with secondary immunodeficiency conditions (e.g., HIV), hepatocellular carcinoma, those on corticosteroids or cytotoxic drugs, pregnant and lactating women, individuals with acute liver failure, or those who did not consent were excluded from the study.

Data collection involved obtaining written informed consent from eligible participants. Demographic and clinical data were collected using a structured proforma. Blood samples were drawn from each patient and analysed for complete blood counts,

liver function tests, serum proteins, serum electrolytes, renal function tests, and ascitic fluid analysis. In addition, ultrasound abdomen evaluations were performed to assess the severity of liver involvement.

The neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) was calculated from the complete blood count data. These patients were subsequently monitored over the course of one year, with follow-up assessments conducted during outpatient visits, inpatient admissions, and via telephone communication. Patients admitted for various complications were thoroughly re-evaluated using the aforementioned investigations. Data analysis was performed using SPSS statistical software and MS Office Excel after the completion of the study period. Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the institutional ethical committee prior to commencement.

Result

The study comprised 140 chronic liver disease patients admitted through inpatient services, with 82.1% being male and 17.9% female. Males make up 82.1% of the sample, with no significant gender differences observed across the NLR groups. Additionally, the mean NLR is slightly higher in males (3.56 ± 1.26) compared to females (3.31 ± 1.16), no statistically significant gender-based difference in NLR. The mean age analysis shows a slight decrease across the NLR groups, from 62.00 ± 4.35 in the ≤ 2 group to 60.89 ± 3.84 in the ≥ 5 group, with the 2-5 group in between (61.11 ± 4.20). However, the p-value of 0.403 indicates that this age difference is not statistically significant.

Table 1: Etiology and NLR group-wise distribution

INR	Alcohol related	Anti HCV	HBSAg	p value
≤ 2	6 (37.5%)	6 (37.5%)	4 (25.0%)	0.55
2-5	43 (41.0%)	26 (24.8%)	36 (34.3%)	
≥ 5	7 (36.8%)	3 (15.8%)	9 (47.4%)	
Total	56	35	49	
INR (Mean \pm SD)	3.57 ± 1.20	3.39 ± 1.26	3.54 ± 1.31	0.8

For alcohol-related cases, 37.5% are in the ≤ 2 group, 41.0% in the 2-5 group, and 36.8% in the ≥ 5 group. For anti-HCV, 37.5% are in the ≤ 2 group, 24.8% in the 2-5 group, and 15.8% in the ≥ 5 group, while for HBSAg, 25.0% are in the ≤ 2 group, 34.3% in the 2-5 group, and 47.4% in the ≥ 5 group.

The total counts for alcohol-related, anti-HCV, and HBSAg cases are 56, 35, and 49, respectively. The mean INR values for alcohol-related cases, anti-HCV, and HBSAg are 3.57 ± 1.20 , 3.39 ± 1.26 , and 3.54 ± 1.31 , respectively, with no significant difference between groups.

Table 2: CTP Class and NLR group-wise distribution

NLR	Class A	Class B	Class C	Total	p value
≤ 2	5 (31.3%)	10 (62.5%)	1 (6.3%)	16	0.001*
2-5	6 (5.7%)	74 (70.5%)	25 (23.8%)	105	
≥ 5	0 (0%)	11 (57.9%)	8 (42.1%)	19	
Total Count	11	95	34	140	
Mean NLR (Mean \pm SD)	2.14 ± 0.78	3.45 ± 1.18	4.14 ± 1.16		0.01*

As per Table 2, In Class A, 31.3% of participants fall in the ≤ 2 group, 62.5% in the 2-5 group, and 0% in the ≥ 5 group. Class B shows 62.5% in the ≤ 2 group, 70.5% in the 2-5 group, and 57.9% in the ≥ 5

group. In Class C, 6.3% are in the ≤ 2 group, 23.8% in the 2-5 group, and 42.1% in the ≥ 5 group. There is a statistically significant difference found in the mean NLR across the different CTP classes.

Table 3: Comparison of blood parameters Across Neutrophil Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) groups.

Blood parameters	NLR Group			Total	p value
	≤ 2	2-5	≥ 5		
Albumin	3.19 \pm 0.89	3.69 \pm 0.81	3.99 \pm 0.76	3.68 \pm 0.83	0.015*
PT	12.02 \pm 2.64	14.55 \pm 3.43	14.16 \pm 3.34	14.21 \pm 3.41	0.021*
S. Bilirubin	1.66 \pm 0.55	2.23 \pm 0.80	2.70 \pm 0.68	2.23 \pm 0.80	0.001*
INR	1.67 \pm 0.36	1.68 \pm 0.37	1.80 \pm 0.35	1.69 \pm 0.37	0.42
Urea	26.08 \pm 6.74	24.57 \pm 7.92	22.06 \pm 6.58	24.40 \pm 7.65	0.27
S. creatinine	1.91 \pm 0.73	1.55 \pm 0.62	1.54 \pm 0.71	1.59 \pm 0.65	0.11
S. Sodium	128.44 \pm 3.52	127.38 \pm 3.21	128.14 \pm 3.47	127.61 \pm 3.28	0.37

As seen in Table 3, Significant differences were observed in albumin levels ($p = 0.015^*$), prothrombin time (PT) ($p = 0.021^*$), and serum bilirubin ($p = 0.001^*$), with higher values in the 2-5 and ≥ 5 NLR groups compared to the ≤ 2 group. However, there were no significant differences in

INR ($p = 0.42$), urea ($p = 0.27$), serum creatinine ($p = 0.11$), or serum sodium ($p = 0.37$) across the NLR groups. The data suggests that albumin, PT, and bilirubin levels vary significantly with NLR, while other blood parameters do not show statistically significant differences across the groups.

Table 4: Comparison of Liver Function Scores (MELD, UKELD, CTP) Across Neutrophil Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) Groups.

NLR Group	≤ 2	2-5	≥ 5	Total	p value
MELD	19.09 \pm 5.54	18.01 \pm 4.75	19.47 \pm 5.59	18.33 \pm 4.96	0.403
MELD-Na	24.99 \pm 4.82	24.99 \pm 3.97	25.51 \pm 4.68	25.06 \pm 4.15	0.88
UKELD	43.92 \pm 2.88	45.11 \pm 2.50	45.72 \pm 2.80	45.05 \pm 2.60	0.116
CTP Score	8.44 \pm 1.5	9.56 \pm 1.4	10.47 \pm 1.3	9.56 \pm 1.5	0.001*

Table 4 analysis reveals no significant differences in MELD ($p = 0.403$), MELD-Na ($p = 0.88$), or UKELD ($p = 0.116$) scores across the NLR groups, indicating that these liver function scores are relatively stable irrespective of the NLR group. However, there is a significant difference in the CTP

score ($p = 0.001^*$), with the CTP score increasing from the ≤ 2 group (8.44 \pm 1.5) to the ≥ 5 group (10.47 \pm 1.3). This suggests that liver function as assessed by the CTP score is influenced by NLR group membership.

Table 5: Correlation of variables with Neutrophil Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR)

NLR	Pearson Correlation	P value
Albumin (gm/dl)	0.171*	0.044*
PT	0.06	0.482
INR	0.04	0.641
S. Bilirubin (mg/dl)	0.363*	0.001*
Urea (mg/dl)	-0.15	0.076
S. creatinine (mg/dl)	-0.101	0.237
S. Sodium	-0.037	0.667
MELD	0.043	0.612
MELD-Na	0.063	0.462
UKELD	0.191*	0.023*
CTP	0.386*	<0.001*

Table 5 presents the correlation of various variables with Neutrophil Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR). Significant positive correlations are observed between NLR and Albumin ($r = 0.171$, $p = 0.044$), S. Bilirubin ($r = 0.363$, $p = 0.001$), UKELD ($r =$

0.191, $p = 0.023$), and CTP ($r = 0.386$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that higher NLR values are associated with higher levels of these parameters. On the other hand, no significant correlations are found with PT ($r = 0.06$, $p = 0.482$), INR ($r = 0.04$, $p = 0.641$), Urea

($r = -0.15$, $p = 0.076$), S. creatinine ($r = -0.101$, $p = 0.237$), S. Sodium ($r = -0.037$, $p = 0.667$), MELD ($r = 0.043$, $p = 0.612$), and MELD-Na ($r = 0.063$, $p =$

0.462), suggesting no meaningful association between NLR and these variables.

Figure 1: Correlation of NLR with Albumin (gm/dl)

Figure 2: Correlation of NLR with S. Bilirubin (mg/dl)

Figure 3: Correlation of NLR with UKELD

Figure 4: Correlation of NLR with CTP

Discussion:

This study highlights significant associations between Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) and liver disease severity, as reflected in Child-Turcotte-Pugh (CTP) and MELD scores. Lower NLR was linked to milder CTP classes, while higher NLR was associated with more severe disease and lower albumin levels, suggesting NLR's potential as a prognostic marker. It also correlated with Prothrombin Time (PT) and serum bilirubin, with higher bilirubin levels being linked to elevated NLR. NLR was found to be significantly associated with CTP scores, underlining its utility alongside CTP and MELD in assessing liver disease severity. Additionally, NLR's relationship with albumin, PT, and bilirubin was marked by significant differences, and it was identified as a useful predictor for ICU transfer, comparable to the APACHE-II score.[8]

Luo et al. demonstrated that pre-operative NLR, rather than ALBI grade, independently predicted overall survival (OS) in HCC patients undergoing hepatectomy. Combining NLR with ALBI improved prognostic accuracy, with higher NLR-ALBI scores correlating with longer hospital stays and poorer outcomes. ROC analysis showed the NLR-ALBI score had a superior AUC compared to NLR or ALBI alone, making it a stronger tool for assessing inflammation and liver function in HCC.[9]

The prognosis of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) patients is influenced by multiple factors such as liver function, tumor grade, and treatment approach. Due to the complexity of these factors, relying on a single clinical index is insufficient. To offer a more comprehensive evaluation, various combinations of indices, including the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) and platelet-to-lymphocyte ratio, have been proposed to better assess patient outcomes.[10]

In Dakshinamoorthy et al.'s study, 38% of patients had an elevated NLR above the normal 2.72, while

62% remained within the normal range. NLR distribution showed 31% below 2, 34% between 2 and 4, 24% above 4, and 3% exceeding 10, the latter group experiencing multiple complications. NLR values ranged from 1.16 to 18.09, with a significant P-value of 0.0021, confirming its reliability in predicting complications in cirrhosis. Alcoholism had no significant impact on outcomes (P = 0.2744).[11]

Moreau et al. found elevated NLR levels in all critically ill cirrhosis patients, with higher values observed in those with Acute-on-Chronic Liver Failure (ACLF). Interestingly, their analysis revealed that the Child-Turcotte-Pugh (CTP) score was more accurate in predicting mortality than NLR, MELD, and CLIF scores, both in the overall cohort and in ACLF patients. This unexpected finding may be due to the higher prevalence of hepatic encephalopathy (HE) in their study compared to previous research.[12]

Traditional prognostic scores like Child-Turcotte-Pugh and MELD have been crucial in predicting outcomes for cirrhosis patients, but newer scores such as NLR have also proven to be accurate mortality predictors, especially in advanced cirrhosis cases in the ICU. Chiriac et al. suggested that both classic and newer scores, such as Child-Turcotte-Pugh and NLR, can effectively stratify prognosis in critically ill cirrhosis patients in the ICU.[7]

In this study, neither the MELD nor MELD-Na scores showed significant differences across the Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) groups (p-values: 0.403 and 0.88, respectively), with scores remaining consistent across the ≤ 2 , 2-5, and ≥ 5 NLR groups. However, previous research has found a correlation between NLR and MELD scores. Hashemi et al. demonstrated that NLR is a strong predictor of adverse outcomes, especially in patients

with bacterial infections, while Moreau et al. showed that NLR can outperform MELD in predicting complications in liver cirrhosis.[13] Both Kalra et al. and Moreau et al. highlighted NLR as a valuable prognostic marker in liver cirrhosis, independent of MELD scores. Kalra et al. emphasized its utility in predicting mortality risk, particularly in patients with low MELD scores. Moreau et al. reinforced the significance of inflammation in prognosis, with higher NLR levels associated with advanced cirrhosis stages. This underscores NLR's potential as a non-invasive and reliable marker for complications in liver cirrhosis. [14,15]

Zhang and colleagues found that higher NLR levels upon admission were linked to an increased one-month mortality risk. Mortality rates rose from 4.9% to 10.7% and 22.6% across different NLR groups. Both univariate and multivariate analyses identified NLR as an independent risk factor for one-month mortality in HBV-related decompensated cirrhosis (HBV-DeCi). Combining NLR and MELD scores improved sensitivity (93.8%) and specificity (81.0%), with high negative predictive values (99.1%). [16]

In the current study, no significant difference was found in UKELD scores across NLR groups (p-value: 0.116), similar to MELD scores. However, a significant difference was observed in CTP scores, with higher NLR groups associated with higher CTP scores, indicating more severe liver disease. Probowati et al. also found a positive correlation between NLR and CTP scores in a study of 33 Indonesian cirrhotic patients.[17] Sungkar et al. found that the Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) was an independent predictor of mortality, with a significant correlation to the Child-Turcotte-Pugh (CTP) score ($r=0.25$; $P=0.002$) [18]. Similarly, in a Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC) cohort, a direct correlation was observed between NLR and CTP score, both serving as prognostic indicators for HCC [19]. Kwon et al. demonstrated that a high NLR was independently linked to one-month survival in CTP class C patients, though the mechanisms behind this association remain unclear [20].

Biyik et al. found that NLR could independently predict mortality in cirrhotic patients, regardless of their CTP and MELD scores, with predictive capability even in those with low scores. [21]

The study highlights a positive correlation of NLR with Albumin, Serum Bilirubin, UKELD, and CTP scores, underscoring its role as a marker of inflammation and liver disease severity. However, NLR shows no significant correlation with coagulation (PT, INR) or kidney function (Creatinine, Sodium). Previous research links NLR with MELD scores in predicting mortality, especially in HBV-related decompensated cirrhosis.

[22]. Elevated NLR is associated with increased hepatic inflammation and poor prognosis in chronic HBV infection [23].

Conclusion:

In conclusion, *A Correlation with CTP and MELD Na Score* demonstrates that Neutrophil Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) is a significant marker in predicting liver disease severity. NLR shows a strong correlation with albumin, bilirubin, UKELD, and CTP scores, indicating its potential as a prognostic tool in chronic liver disease (CLD) patients. Although NLR did not show significant relationships with other liver function scores like MELD and MELD-Na, its association with CTP class and liver function suggests its value in clinical assessments. Further studies with larger sample sizes are needed to establish NLR as a standard predictive tool for survival in CLD.

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